

Seismic Analysis of a Multi-Storied Steel Building Provided with Different Types of Damper and Base Isolation

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Abstract— This paper presents the steel design of multi-storey steel framed buildings (MSSB) and the analysis of different dampers and base isolations in various seismic zones. Steel buildings are easy to build and gives more strength, also after demolish there are scrap value so ties more economical. Base isolation giving the structural safety and also safety for peoples and goods in the building. For the retrofit of the historic buildings base isolation is also used. In the present manuscript work done on, Seismic analysis of G+10 multi storied steel building with and without dampers (viscous damper and friction damper) and base isolation system (friction isolation and lead plug bearing). Stabilization of steel building in the different types of seismic provision which one is more suitable according to seismic zone has been analyzed. In this work used seismic zone II, zone III, zone IV and zone V by using ETABs software analysis carried out. Found the optimum damper and base isolation also their combination effect in the steel building at various zone as per analysis result of responses (viz. storey drift, storey displacement, base shear) by response spectrum method.

Keywords— MSSB, seismic zones, Damper, Base isolation, ETABs.

I. Introduction

Earthquake is one of the natural disaster that challenge most of the engineers of the construction industry [2]. It may cause serious injuries and damage due to destruction of the building. Structural engineers have been working on the characterization and measurement of structural damage for many years. The different approaches to characterize damage such as ductility, drift ratio, maximum deformation, strain softening and energy dissipation characteristics at component, element or structural level [5]. When existing buildings are retrofitted, the process becomes easier with dampers than with the base isolators [3]. According to literature base isolation helps to reduce drift and energy dissipation.

The multi storied buildings being built is increasing day by day, more than 4 storied building this called as multi storied and below that this are low rise building [8]. Steel used in building construction mostly because its light weight structure, eco-friendly due to use again and again also economical due to its pleasant scrap value. The most important feature of steel used in large constructions is its flexibility, which allows it to be bent without breaking. Steel structures are particularly good at providing energy dissipation capabilities.. It's a material which has high strength per unit mass. Function of all the structure is that it with stand stressed due to load that is wind, earthquake, without failure or undue distress such as excessive deflection [7].

Seismic isolation is a system in which buildings or other structures are uncoupled from the strongest impacts of earthquake motions. Amplitude of studies has been done in the field of seismic isolation [2], [5], [6], [7], [8]. These all implements have been classified as elastomeric bearing and sliding bearing. Natural Rubber Bearings, Low-Damping Rubber Bearings, Lead-Rubber Bearings, High-Damping Rubber Bearing are examples of the electrometric bearing. However, friction pendulum system (FPS), double concave friction pendulum system (DCFP) and triple concave friction pendulum system (TCFP) are popular types of plain bearings [9]. Other type of friction isolator is the Lateral Impact Double-elastic Concave Friction Pendulum (LIR-DCFP), which has

been proposed to the internal impact of the DCFP and thereby limits its failure [10]. In addition, plot bearings (PB) are another type of bearings consisting of sliding parts used in the preparation of hybrid insulation systems, and these bearings are used in models with other systems.

Based on the merits of FSD in past investigations and also its seismic behavior in actual projects [4], this device has effectively worked in saving stability of structures against earthquakes and providing dissipation. While previous works have studied on the application of FVD, VD and its effectiveness, there is a lack of research comparing the productivity of FVD to other seismic-resistant devices, such as base isolators. To close this research gap, a new combination of seismic devices for buildings, including FVD and isolation devices, was proposed and the seismic performance of the combination was calculated and compared with fixed-base models and other conventional base isolators, such as LRB and FPS.

Figure 1: Without and with base isolation

(<https://www.researchgate.net/figure/Conventional-system-VS-base-isolation-system>)

II. Literature Review

Vaibhav Srivastava, Rishabh Joshi, Kamal Kumar, Rifat Resatoglu, Mohd Zain, Anjali Singh (April 2023) “Effect of seismic load on behavior of RCC, composite and light steel building analysed using ETABS software: A comparative study”.

In the present study, seismic performance of a G + 3 residential building which is located in Earthquake Zone II is evaluated using Equivalent Static Method of seismic analysis for composite and light steel frame building over RCC construction. The 3D model for each type of structures i.e., RCC, composite and light steel building is modelled separately and compared with each other for cost analysis. Steel framing is a light weight structure and more advantage over conventional RCC construction. In composite construction, the properties of RCC and steel structures are combined adding to more advantages. ETABS 2016 software is used and results are compared on the basis of story drift, maximum story displacement, shear force and bending moment.

Kashif Javaid, Nitin Verma (February 2023) “Seismic performance of irregular composite buildings: A comparative study of the effectiveness of buckling restrained braces and viscous dampers”.

In this research used Restrained Buckling Braces (BRBs) and Viscous Dampers (VDs) on the 15-story steel–concrete composite moment-resisting frames. A comprehensive response spectrum analysis was carried out. Result was VDs being more efficient in reducing the time period and base shear by 65–73% and 80–90% respectively and BRBs reducing the max. overturning moment in irregular building configurations. In concluded, the study found that VDs are more effective seismic control devices for composite buildings, use should be based on a trade-off analysis as per specific needs of the building.

Harpreet Singh, Aditya Kumar Tiwary (Nov 2022) “ Dynamic analysis of RCC framed structure considering effect of viscous dampers and base isolation”.

This study analyzed a G + 10 Story building using composite columns, viscous dampers, and base isolation techniques. In this paper was check the efficacy of viscous dampers and base isolation techniques for controlling the response of the composite column structure. After completed study, composite columns and viscous damper combination reduce the Story displacement and drift values but increase the base shear values. After the study, it's had been found that a combination of composite columns, viscous dampers, and a base isolation provision is highly helpful in controlling the seismic response of the structure.

In this paper the investigation was carried on earthquake resistance structure made by adopting the dampers for different storied building with bay size of 5 X 5 m and storey height of 3m using E-tabs software. Study is carried with and without the building analysis is carried by response spectrum method by using ETABs 2016 software. The parameters are studied are Base shear, storey stiffness, lateral drift, time period and effectiveness of damper.

Ketan Patela, Sonal Thakkar(2013) “Analysis of CFT, RCC and Steel Building Subjected to Lateral Loading”.

In this research a comparative study of different types of building has done. 10, 20 and 30 storey building has used in each type. In that building included concrete filled steel tube(CFT), RCC and steel building. In that paper, explore the behavior of buildings constructed using various materials when subjected to lateral loads. The study focuses on three common building materials that is Concrete-filled steel tube (CFT), reinforced concrete (RCC), and steel. Through analysis, the authors investigate how each material responds to lateral loading, examining factors such as structural stability, deformation characteristics, and overall performance under dynamic forces. By comparing the stability behavior of buildings constructed with these materials, the paper offers insights into the strengths and weaknesses of each construction method in withstanding lateral loads, providing valuable information for engineers and designers in optimizing building designs for safety and structural integrity in seismic or wind-prone regions.

Gang Xu, Tong Guo, Aiqun Li, Shiyuan Wang, Ruijun Zhang, Ruizhao Zhu, Jun Xu (2023)“Review on Self-Centering Damper for Seismic Resilient Building Structures”.

In this paper observed that traditional dampers can't automatically replace its original position so researchers proposed to combine self-centering devices with traditional dampers to obtain good self-centering capacity, also self-centering dampers can avoid post-earthquake damage of the structure. In damper including steel yield dampers, friction dampers, viscoelastic dampers, viscous fluid dampers, etc. In China, New Zealand and Japan more earthquake due to that building frame structures moderate damaged, which required to rebuilt. Therefore, necessity to improve the seismic performance has been mostly concerned. This paper concerned future directions in the further research which is beneficial to the farther engineering popularization and application of self-centering dampers.

Junji Toyama, Yozo Shinozaki, Tetsushiro Inoue, Ryota Maseki, Ichiro Nagashima, Masayoshi Takagi, Yoshikazu Kitagawa (2004) “An Advanced Base-Isolation System for Irregular Building Design”.

In that gives the information on the use of a semi-active base isolation system combining variable oil dampers with the conventional passive base isolation system with time story response analysis. This system was improved to moderate the acceleration during little quantity and medium earthquakes certified in Japan. High rise and low-rise symmetric building used with connect these two structure each other. Base isolation system can't use when building frame high in structural stability. This concluded that in small or medium earthquake base isolation system will reducing acceleration.

III. Research gap

Literature is carried out on regular steel or RCC building and irregular steel building by specific seismic method but not using various seismic zones. In some paper analysis done using comparison between different seismic method. A lot of studies have been carried out by seismic providing bracing, damper, shear wall and isolation system separately for seismic and wind stability for RCC building but also there are more types in individual technique and not research carried out comparative analysis between them. A very few studies on multi storied steel building with damper and base isolation have been reported in the literature. Lack result of combination effect of dampers and isolation system on structures. All work of analysis and design mostly carried out in ETABs software. Further, these studies are done by considering various building heights, various seismic zone and mostly consider medium soil type for linear static and dynamic analysis. No significant study reported on behavior of multi-storied steel building provided with comparison analysis of different types of damper and base isolation technique at different seismic zone. Damper and base isolation combination effect on preliminary steel building at different seismic zone.

IV. Objectives

Problem statement

In the research carried out Seismic analysis of G+10 multi storied steel building with and without dampers (viscous damper and friction damper) and base isolation system (friction isolation and lead plug bearing) at seismic zone II, zone III, zone IV, zone V by using ETABs software. Study the optimum damper, optimum base isolation and thete combination effect in the steel building, Also analysis result of responses (viz. storey drift, storey displacement, base shear).

Research objectives

The following are the objectives of the dissertation work:

- Analyse and design of multi storied steel building (MSSB) using ETABs software to determining the response (viz. storey drift, storey displacement and base shear) without damper, base isolation system and considering the building location in earthquake zone.
- To determine most efficient type of damper (viscous damper, friction damper) and efficient type of base isolation technique (friction pendulum system, lead plug bearing).
- To determine optimum damper and base isolation combination effect in the multi storied steel building at different seismic zone.
- To compare the analysis results of responses (viz. storey drift, storey displacement, Base shear) obtained for the multistorey steel building with different conditions.

V. Geometrical details of multi-storey steel building

The geometrical details considered for the analysis of MSSB is shown in Table 5.1

TABLE I: GEOMETRICAL DETAILS OF THE MSSB

Parameters	Particulars	Parameters	Particulars
Height of structure	33 m	No. of stories	G+10
		Height of each storey	3m
Plan dimensions	15m x 15m	Plan area	225 m ²
Floor to floor height	3m	Plan dimension	15m X 15m
Size of column and concrete grade	ISWB 175-ISWB 600; ISMB 100-ISMB 600; ISHB 150-ISHB 450; ISLB 100-ISLB 400, Fe 345	Wall thickness	150 mm
		Soil type	Medium
Size of beam and concrete grade	ISLB 75-ISLB 175; ISHB 75-ISHB 225, Fe 345	Dead load	Self-weight of structural element
Deck slab thickness and concrete grade	0.15m, M25	Live load	4 kN/m ²
Importance factor	I = 1	Type of building	Commercial
Response reduction factor	R = 5	Seismic zone	II, III, IV, V

A. Analysis of multi-storey steel building

Analysis of MSSB with damper (fluid viscous damper, friction damper) and base isolation system at different locations zones (Zone II, III, IV, V) is performed by developing the models for find optimum seismic provision and then combination of optimum damper and base isolation considered on medium soil type using ETABS software.

Figure 2: Modelling of MSSB without damper and base isolation (Plan and 3D View)

Figure 3: Modelling of MSSB is pass all steel frames

B. Modelling of building

Modelling and analysis of building is done by ETABS software. Analysis of G+10 storey building with and without damper and base isolation system is done before designing need all steel frame are pass stress capacity (fig. 3). The various models are prepared by using ETABS software for calculating optimum type of seismic provision in specific seismic zone. Total 24 model has been done in that four model of without any seismic provision (fig.2) and four model of each seismic provision in that viscous damper (fig. 4.a), friction damper (fig. 4.b), lead plug bearing (fig. 5.a), friction pendulum system (fig. 5.b) also combination of damper and base isolation.

Types of damper (a) viscous damper (b) friction damper

Figure 4 (a, b): 3D Models of MSSB provided with damper at corner

Types of base isolation (a) lead plug bearing (b) friction pendulum system
 Figure 5 (a, b): 3D Models of MSSB provided with base isolation at column base

VI. Results and Discussion

preliminary MSSB result more than the permissible limit that's why done the seismic provision. MSSB with provided seismic provision reduced displacement value in that damper reduces 62.45% to 97% and base isolation reduces 4.65% to 15.52% displacement as per different seismic zone. The variations in the displacement values of the MSSB provided with dampers and isolations at different zones is graphically represented in Figure 6.

Graph 1: Variation in storey displacement for MSSB with types of damper and base isolation at zone II, III, VI, V

the MSSB with provided seismic provision this reduced drift value in that damper reduces 69.29% to 82.16% and base isolation dose not reduces the drift value it remains same as to preliminary value, means base isolation doesn't work on storey drift. . Base isolation in that lead plug bearing and friction pendulum system used in MSSB at zone II and III gives same results of drift and at zone VI and V the variation has 28.43%.

Graph 2: Variation in storey drift for MSSB with types of damper and base isolation at zone II, III, VI, V

In the MSSB results shows with provided seismic provision reduced base shear value at zone II and III. Means that for increasing load carrying capacity doesn't need of seismic provision at zone II and III. Provision of friction damper and FPS combination system gain base shear at zone VI and V up to 5.47%. At zone VI and V provision of friction damper, LRB and FPS gain base shear has 1.32% to 2.48%.

Graph 3: Variation in base shear for MSSB with types of damper and base isolation at zone II, III, VI, V

A. Optimum location of damper

From the analysis results, it is found that the MSSB provided with types of damper at the zone II, III, VI and V. It has provided minimum values for all the seismic responses in the all seismic zone when fluid viscous damper provided at corner and friction damper provided at alternate storey (fig. 6).

Figure 6: Optimum position of FVD and FD in seismic zone II, III, VI, V

VII. Conclusions

- i. The displacement and drift of MSSB provided without seismic provision means preliminary building result are 16 to 20% more than the permissible limit hence need to provide seismic provision. So, used damper in that VD and FD also used base isolation in that LPB and FPS.
- ii. Maximum storey displacement at zone II and zone III minimizes by VD the rate of 86.54% and 86.07% respectively than the FD, LRB and FPS. Maximum storey drift reduces by VD the rate of 92.39% and 91.78% than the other provision at zone II and zone III.
- iii. All over this observed that optimum damper are VD and optimum base isolation system are LRB at zone II and zone III. their combination effect reduced displacement and drift are 90.38% and 48.66% respectively for zone II, are 97.61% and 98.46% respectively for zone III .
- iv. At zone VI and V by friction damper minimize more displacement and drift of structure than viscous damper a rate of 66.93% and 47.32%. In base isolation FPS minimize displacement and drift than the LPB a rate of 4.3% and 28.45% respectively. Therefore, the combination of friction damper and FPS reduces the displacement and drift are 87.58% and 79.71% respectively also gain the base shear 5.29%.
- v. It is concluded that the combination of friction damper and Friction pendulum system (FPS) gives greater seismic response result than other seismic provision at zone IV and V. The results confirm that the presence of a damper leads to higher displacement and drift values. However, when provided base isolation its improve the base shear value. Hence, combined with base isolation at zone VI and zone V, it not only amplifies the base shear but also enhances the load carrying capacity of the structure

A. Future scope

- i. Study of the behavior of multi storied steel building for multi-level outrigger system.

- ii. It can be done for bridge analysis also.
- iii. A model can be made with various shapes of base isolations and compare their effect on structure.
- iv. Different type of damper and base isolation can compare at various seismic zones and at different soil conditions.
- v. Regular and irregular structure with steel frame and seismic provision and can compare their lateral load effect on structural parameters.

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